

Supplementary information

**Psychotherapies for depression in children and adolescents: a systematic
review and network meta-analysis**

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Lin, John Weisz, Eirini Karyotaki, Yvonne Stikkelbroek, Mathias Harrer

World Psychiatry, 2027

Supplement A. Search strings

PubMed

Psychotherapy [MH] OR psychotherap*[All Fields] OR cbt[All Fields] OR "behavior therapies"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapy"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapeutic"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapeutical"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapeutics"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapist"[All Fields] OR "behavior therapists"[All Fields] OR "behavior treatment"[All Fields] OR "behavior treatments"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapies"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapy"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapeutics"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapeutic"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapeutical"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapist"[All Fields] OR "behaviors therapists"[All Fields] OR "behaviors treatment"[All Fields] OR "behaviors treatments"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapies"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapy"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapeutics"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapeutic"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapeutical"[All Fields] OR "behavioral therapist"[All Fields] OR "behavioral 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control training"[All Fields] OR "self control trainings"[All Fields] AND (Depressive Disorder[MH] OR Depression[MH] OR dysthymi*[All Fields] OR "affective disorder"[All Fields] OR "affective disorders"[All Fields] OR "mood disorder"[All Fields] OR "mood disorders"[All Fields] OR depression*[All

Fields] OR depressive*[All Fields] OR "dysthymic disorder"[MeSH Terms])

Limits: RCTs

Embase

#1 'psychotherapy'/exp OR 'psychotherapy' OR 'psychotherapies' OR 'psychotherapeutics' OR 'psychotherapeutical' OR 'cognitive therapy'/exp OR 'cognitive behavior therapy'/exp OR 'behavior therapy'/exp OR 'cbt' OR 'cognitive behavioural therapy' OR 'cognitive behavioural therapies' OR 'cognitive behavioral therapy' OR 'cognitive behavioral therapies' OR 'behavior therapy' OR 'behavior therapies' OR 'behaviour therapy' OR 'behaviour therapies' OR 'cognition therapy' OR 'cognitive therapies' OR 'cognitive therapy' OR 'cognitive therapeutic' OR 'cognitive therapeutics' OR 'cognitive therapeutical' OR 'cognitive therapist' OR 'cognitive therapists' OR 'cognitive treatment' OR 'cognitive treatments' OR 'cognitive restructuring' OR 'cognition therapies' OR 'cognition therapie' OR 'cognition therapeutical' OR 'cognition therapeutic' OR 'cognition therapeutics' OR 'cognition therapist' OR 'cognition therapists' OR 'cognition treatment' OR 'cognition treatments' OR 'behavior therapeutic' OR 'behavior therapeutical' OR 'behavior therapeutics' OR 'behavior therapist' OR 'behavior therapists' OR 'behavior treatment' OR 'behavior treatments' OR 'behaviors therapies' OR 'behaviors therapy' OR 'behaviors therapeutics' OR 'behaviors therapeutic' OR 'behaviors therapeutical' OR 'behaviors therapist' OR 'behaviors therapists' OR 'behaviors treatment' OR 'behaviors treatments' OR 'behavioral therapies' OR 'behavioral therapy' OR 'behavioral therapeutics' OR 'behavioral therapeutic' OR 'behavioral therapeutical' OR 'behavioral therapist' OR 'behavioral therapists' OR 'behavioral treatment' OR 'behavioral treatments' OR 'behaviour therapeutic' OR 'behaviour therapeutical' OR 'behaviour therapeutics' OR 'behaviour therapist' OR 'behaviour therapists' OR 'behaviour treatment' OR 'behaviour treatments' OR 'behaviours therapies' OR 'behaviours therapy' OR 'behaviours therapeutics' OR 'behaviours therapeutic' OR 'behaviours therapeutical' OR 'behaviours therapist' OR 'behaviours therapists' OR 'behaviours treatment' OR 'behaviours treatments' OR 'behavioural therapies' OR 'behavioural therapy' OR 'behavioural therapeutics' OR 'behavioural therapeutic' OR 'behavioural therapeutical' OR 'behavioural therapist' OR 'behavioural therapists' OR 'behavioural treatment' OR 'behavioural treatments' OR 'behaviors activation' OR 'behaviors activation' OR 'behavioral activation' OR 'behaviour activation' OR 'behaviours activation' OR 'behavioural activation' OR 'psychoanalytic therapy'/exp OR 'psychodynamic' OR 'psychodynamical' OR 'psychoanalysis' OR 'psychoanalytical' OR 'counselling'/exp OR 'counseling'/exp OR 'counselling' OR 'counseling' OR 'problem-solving' OR 'problem solving' OR 'supportive therapy' OR 'metacognitive therapy' OR 'metacognitive therapies' OR 'metacognitive therapeutic' OR 'metacognitive therapeutics' OR 'metacognitive therapeutical' OR 'metacognitive therapist' OR 'metacognitive therapists' OR 'metacognitive treatment' OR 'metacognitive treatments' OR 'meta-cognitive therapy' OR 'meta-cognitive therapies' OR 'meta-cognitive therapeutical' OR 'meta-cognitive therapists' OR 'meta-cognitive treatment' OR 'meta-cognitive treatments' OR 'solution-focused therapies' OR 'solution focused therapies' OR 'solution-focussed therapies' OR 'solution focused therapy' OR 'solution-focused therapy' OR 'solution focused therapy' OR 'solution-focussed therapy' OR 'solution focused therapy' OR 'solution-focused therapeutic' OR 'solution focused therapeutic' OR 'solution-focussed therapeutic' OR 'solution focussed therapy' OR 'solution-focussed therapy' OR 'solution-focused therapeutics' OR 'solution focused therapeutics' OR 'solution-focussed therapeutics' OR 'solution focused therapeutics' OR 'solution-focused therapeutical' OR 'solution focused therapeutical' OR 'solution-focussed therapeutical' OR 'solution focused therapeutical' OR 'self-control therapies' OR 'self control therapies' OR 'self-control therapy' OR 'self control therapy' OR 'self-control therapeutics' OR 'self control therapeutics' OR 'self-control therapeutical' OR 'self control therapeutical' OR 'self-control therapeutic' OR 'self control therapeutic' OR 'self-control training' OR 'self control training' OR 'self control trainings' OR 'self-control trainings' OR 'mindfulness' OR 'acceptance commitment' OR 'acceptance and commitment' OR 'assertiveness training'

#2 'compassion-focused' OR 'compassion-focussed' OR 'compassion focused' OR 'compassion focussed' OR 'constructivist' OR 'constructivists'

#3 'therapies' OR 'therapy' OR 'therapeutics' OR 'therapist' OR 'treatment' OR 'treatments'

#4 Combine: #2 AND #3

#5: #1 OR #4

#6 'depressive disorder'/exp OR 'depression'/exp OR 'depressive' OR 'major depression'/exp OR 'major depressive disorder'/exp OR 'depression' OR 'depressions' OR 'depressive' OR 'dysthymic disorder'/exp OR 'dysthymic disorder' OR 'dysthymia'/exp OR 'dysthymic' OR 'mood disorder'/exp OR 'affective disorder'/exp OR 'affective disorder' OR 'affective disorders' OR 'mood disorder' OR 'mood disorders'

Combine: #5 AND #6

Limits: RCTs

PsycINFO

(DE "Psychotherapy" OR "Psychotherapy" OR "psychotherapies" OR "psychotherapeutic" OR "psychotherapeutical" OR "psychotherapeutics" OR DE "Behavior Therapy" OR DE "Cognitive Behavior Therapy" OR "CBT" OR "behavior therapies" OR "behavior therapy" OR "behavior therapeutic" OR "behavior therapeutical" OR "behavior therapeutics" OR "behavior therapist" OR "behavior therapists" OR "behavior treatment" OR "behavior treatments" OR "behaviors therapies" OR "behaviors therapy" OR "behaviors therapeutics" OR "behaviors therapeutic" OR "behaviors therapeutical" OR "behaviors therapist" OR "behaviors therapists" OR "behaviors treatment" OR "behaviors

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AND

(DE "Depression (Emotion)" "depressive disorder" OR "depression" OR "depressions" OR "depressive" OR DE "Major Depression" OR "major depression" OR "major depressive disorder" OR DE "Dysthymic Disorder" OR "Dysthymia" OR "dysthymic disorder" OR DE "Affective Disorders" OR "Affective Disorder" OR "affective disorders" OR "Mood Disorder" OR "Mood disorders")

Limits: Methodology is ME=(treatment outcome/clinical trial): papers

Cochrane

- #1 MeSH descriptor: [Depressive Disorder] explode all trees : 6, 777
- #2 "depress*" (Word variations have been searched) : 51, 768
- #3 #1or#2 :51,783
- #4 "major depressive disorder" (Word variations have been searched) : 5, 435
- #5 #3or#4 :51,783
- #6 MeSH descriptor: [Dysthymic Disorder] explode all trees : 129
- #7 "dysthymi*" (Word variations have been searched) : 649
- #8 #6or#7 :649
- #9 #5or#8 :51,800
- #10 "mood disorder" (Word variations have been searched) :4, 034
- #11 "affective disorder" (Word variations have been searched) : 2, 882
- #12 #10or#11:6,055
- #13 #9or#12:53,227
- #14 MeSH descriptor: [Psychotherapy] explode all trees : 13, 568
- #15 "psychotherap*" (Word variations have been searched) : 7, 758
- #16 "CBT" (Word variations have been searched) : 2, 029
- #17 "Cognitive Behav* therap*" (Word variations have been searched) : 8, 893

#18 #14or#15or#16or#17 :20,795
#19 'psychodynamic" (Word variations have been searched) : 469
#20 MeSH descriptor: [Psychoanalysis] explode all trees : 13
#21 "psychoanaly*" (Word variations have been searched) : 345
#22 MeSH descriptor: [Counseling] explode all trees : 2, 783
#23 "counseling*" (Word variations have been searched) : 6, 913
#24 "problem solving" (Word variations have been searched) : 2, 867
#25 #18or#19or#20or#21or#22or#23or#24 :28,149
#26 "acceptance commitment" (Word variations have been searched) : 168
#27 "assertiveness training" (Word variations have been searched) :231
#28 "behavior activation" (Word variations have been searched) : 663
#29 "mindfulness" (Word variations have been searched) : 466
#30 "metacognitive therap*" (Word variations have been searched) :56
#31 "solution focused therap*" (Word variations have been searched) :858
#32 "self control training" (Word variations have been searched): 5850
#33 #25or#26or#27or#28or#29or#30or#31or#32 :32,748
#34 "Randomized Controlled Trial":ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched) : 120, 901
#35 #13 and #33 and #34 in Trials

Supplement B. Previous meta-analyses

- Bevilacqua L, Fox-Smith L, Lampard O et al. *Clin Child Psychol Psychiatry* 2024;29:1349-64.
- Chen B, Li J, Qi Y et al. *BMC Psychiatry* 2025;25:321.
- Dippel N, Szota K, Cuijpers P et al. *Psychol Psychother Theory Res Pract* 2022;95:656-79.
- Eckshtain D, Horn R, Weisz JR. *Child Psychiatry Hum Dev* 2023;54:1737-48.
- Eckshtain D, Kuppens S, Ugueto A et al. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 2020;59:45-63.
- Liu P, Situ M, Duan X et al. *J Evid Based Med* 2024;17:740-57.
- López-Pinar C, Lara-Merín L, Macías J. *J Affect Disord* 2025;368:633-44.
- van Aswegen T, Samartzi E, Morris L et al. *Int J Psychol* 2023;58:499-511.
- Waraan L, Siqveland J, Hanssen-Bauer K et al. *Clin Child Psychol Psychiatry* 2023;28:831-49.
- Zhou X, Hetrick SE, Cuijpers P et al. *World Psychiatry* 2015;14:207-22.
- Zhou X, Teng T, Zhang Y et al. *Lancet Psychiatry* 2020;7:581-601.

Supplement C. Definitions of therapies and control conditions

<i>Condition</i>	<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Source</i>
Cognitive behavior therapy	CBT	In CBT the therapists focus on the impact a patient's present dysfunctional thoughts have on current behavior and future functioning. CBT is aimed at evaluating, challenging and modifying a patient's dysfunctional beliefs (cognitive restructuring). In this form of treatment the therapist mostly emphasizes homework assignments and outside-of-session activities. Therapists exert an active influence over therapeutic interactions and topics of discussion, use a psycho educational approach, and teach patients new ways of coping with stressful situations.	Cuijpers et al., 2020
Family therapy	FAM	FT works with families to nurture change and development. FT tends to view change in terms of the systems of interaction between family members. In the case of youth with MDD, FT aims at helping the family to answer the child's needs for completing age-appropriate developmental tasks to relieve depression.	Zhou et al., 2020
Behavioral activation therapy	BAT	We considered an intervention to be behavioral activation when the registration of pleasant activities and the increase of positive interactions between a person and his or her environment were the core elements of the treatment. Social skills training could be a part of the intervention.	Cuijpers et al., 2020
Interpersonal psychotherapy	IPT	IPT is a brief and highly structured manual-based psychotherapy that addresses interpersonal issues in depression, to the exclusion of all other foci of clinical attention. IPT has no specific theoretical origin although its theoretical basis can be seen as coming from the work of Sullivan, Meyer, and Bowlby. The current form of the treatment was developed by the late Gerald Klerman and Myrna Weissman in the 1980s.	Cuijpers et al., 2020
Supportive therapy	SUP	We defined supportive therapy as any unstructured therapy without specific psychological techniques other than those common to all approaches such as helping people to ventilate their experiences and emotions and offering empathy. It is not aimed at solutions, or acquiring new skills. It is based on the assumption that relief from personal problems may be achieved through discussion with others. These non-directive therapies are commonly described in the literature as either counseling or non-directive therapy.	Cuijpers et al., 2020
Problem-solving therapy	PST	We defined PST as a psychological intervention in which the following elements had to be included: definition of personal problems, generation of multiple solutions to each problem, selection of the best solution, the working out of a systematic plan for this solution, and evaluation as to whether the solution has resolved the problem.	Cuijpers et al., 2020
Relaxation therapy	REL	Relaxation treatment (also known as relaxation therapy or training) is defined as a set of therapeutic exercises and strategies designed to help individuals decrease physical and psychological tension and anxiety. It is an umbrella term that encompasses several specific evidence-based techniques, including Progressive Muscle Relaxation, Autogenic Training, Guided Imagery and Breathing Exercises.	StatPearls, 2023
Care-as-usual	CAU	CAU was defined as the standard care participants received in their respective study setting, without any additional structured psychological intervention provided by the research team.	Cuijpers et al., 2021
Other control conditions	OthCTR	Conditions that were explicitly used as a control condition, but did offer some kind of active component, such as psychoeducation, tutoring or attention control.	This paper
Waiting list	WL	WL is a control condition in which the participants receive no active treatment during the study but are forewarned that they can receive one after the study period is over.	Cuijpers et al., 2024

Sources

- Cuijpers P, Karyotaki E, de Wit L et al. *Psychother Res* 2020;30:279-93.
- Cuijpers P, Miguel C, Harrer M et al. *Epidemiol Psychiatr Sci* 2024;33:e56.
- Cuijpers P, Quero S, Papola D et al. *Psychol Med* 2021;51:634-44.
- Norelli SK, Long A, Krepps JM. *Relaxation techniques*. Treasure Island: StatPearls Publishing, 2026.
- Zhou X, Teng T, Zhang Y et al. *Lancet Psychiatry* 2020;7:581-601.

Supplement D. References of included studies

<i>Study</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Ackerson, 1998	Ackerson J, Scogin F, McKendree-Smith N et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 1998;66:685-90.
Andersson, 2022	Andersson R, Ahlen J, Mataix-Cols D et al. <i>BMJ Open</i> 2022;12:e066357.
Arnarson, 2009	Arnarson EÖ, Craighead WE. <i>Behav Res Ther</i> 2009;47:577-85.
Asarnow, 2002	Asarnow JR, Scott CV, Mintz J. <i>Cogn Ther Res</i> 2002;26:221-9.
Bolton, 2007	Bolton P, Bass J, Betancourt T et al. <i>JAMA</i> 2007;298:519-27.
Brent, 1997	Brent DA, Holder D, Kolko D et al. <i>Arch Gen Psychiatry</i> 1997;54:877-85.
Casella, 2025	Casella CB, Farhat LC, Labbadia EM et al. <i>J Adolesc Health</i> 2025;77:472-83.
Charkhandeh, 2016	Charkhandeh M, Talib MA, Hunt CJ. <i>Psychiatry Res</i> 2016;239:325-30.
Clarke, 1995	Clarke GN, Hawkins W, Murphy M et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 1995;34:312-21.
Clarke, 1999	Clarke GN, Rohde P, Lewinsohn PM et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 1999;38:272-9.
Clarke, 2001	Clarke GN, Hornbrook M, Lynch F et al. <i>Arch Gen Psychiatry</i> 2001;58:1127-34.
Clarke, 2002	Clarke GN, Hornbrook M, Lynch F et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2002;41:305-13.
Curry, 2022	Curry JF, Kaminer Y, Goldston DB et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2022;61:508-19.
De Cuyper, 2004	De Cuyper S, Timbremont B, Braet C et al. <i>Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2004;13:105-14.
De Jonge-Heesen, 2020	De Jonge-Heesen KWJ, Rasing SPA, Vermulst AA et al. <i>BMC Med</i> 2020;18:188.
Diamond, 2002	Diamond GS, Reis BF, Diamond GM et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2002;41:1190-6.
Diamond, 2010	Diamond GS, Wintersteen MB, Brown GK et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2010;49:122-31.
Dietz, 2015	Dietz LJ, Weinberg RJ, Brent DA et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2015;54:191-9.
Do, 2021	Do R, Lee S, Kim JS et al. <i>J Affect Disord</i> 2021;282:885-93.
Duong, 2016	Duong MT, Cruz RA, King KM et al. <i>Prev Sci</i> 2016;17:295-305.
Gillham, 2006	Gillham JE, Hamilton J, Freres DR et al. <i>J Abnorm Child Psychol</i> 2006;34: 195-211.
Goodyer, 2017	Goodyer IM, Reynolds S, Barrett B et al. <i>Health Technol Assess</i> 2017;21:1-94.
Grudin, 2022	Grudin R, Ahlen J, Mataix-Cols D et al. <i>BMJ Open</i> 2022;12:e066357.
Gudmundsen, 2016	Gudmundsen G, McCauley E, Schloretdt K et al. <i>J Clin Child Adolesc Psychol</i> 2016;45:291-304.
He, 2026	He Q, Li J, Wang J et al. <i>J Affect Disord</i> 2026;394(Pt. A):120559.
Idsoe, 2019	Idsoe T, Keles S, Olseth AR et al. <i>BMC Psychiatry</i> 2019;19:155.
Israel, 2013	Israel P, Diamond GS. <i>Clin Child Psychol Psychiatry</i> 2013;18:334-50.
Kahn, 1990	Kahn JS, Kehle TJ, Jenson WR et al. <i>Sch Psychol Rev</i> 1990;19:196-211.
Kitchen, 2021	Kitchen CEW, Tiffin PA, Lewis S et al. <i>Child Adolesc Ment Health</i> 2021;26:290-5.
Kobak, 2015	Kobak KA, Mundt JC, Kennard B. <i>Ann Gen Psychiatry</i> 2015;14:37.
Lewinsohn, 1990	Lewinsohn PM, Clarke GN, Hops H et al. <i>Behav Ther</i> 1990;21:385-401.
Liddle, 1990	Liddle B, Spence SH. <i>Behav Cogn Psychother</i> 1990;18:85-102.
Lindqvist, 2020	Lindqvist K, Mechler J, Carlbring P et al. <i>J Med Internet Res</i> 2020;22:e18047.
Listug-Lunde, 2013	Listug-Lunde L, Vogeltanz-Holm N, Collins J. <i>Am Indian Alsk Native Ment Health Res</i> 2013;20:16-34.
Luby, 2012	Luby J, Lenze S, Tillman R. <i>J Child Psychol Psychiatry</i> 2012;53:313-22.
Martinez, 2019	Martínez V, Rojas G, Martínez P, Gaete J et al. <i>Front Psychiatry</i> 2019;10:552.

Martinovic, 2006	Martinovic Ž, Simonovic P, Djokic R. <i>Epilepsy Behav</i> 2006;9:619-24.
McCarty, 2013	McCarty CA, Violette HD, Duong MT et al. <i>J Clin Child Adolesc Psychol</i> 2013;42:554-63.
Mechler, 2022	Mechler J, Lindqvist K, Carlbring P et al. <i>Lancet Digit Health</i> 2022;4:e594-603.
Moeini, 2019	Moeini B, Bashirian S, Soltanian AR et al. <i>J Res Health Sci</i> 2019;19:e00454.
Mufson, 1999	Mufson L, Weissman MM, Moreau D et al. <i>Arch Gen Psychiatry</i> 1999;56:573-9.
Mufson, 2004	Mufson L, Dorta KP, Wickramaratne P et al. <i>Arch Gen Psychiatry</i> 2004;61:577-84.
O'Dea, 2024	O'Dea B, Li SH, Subotic-Kerry M et al. medRxiv 2024.11.17.24317363.
Poole, 2018	Poole LA, Knight T, Toumbourou JW et al. <i>J Abnorm Child Psychol</i> 2018;46:169-81.
Poppelaars, 2016	Poppelaars M, Tak YR, Lichtwarck-Aschoff A et al. <i>Behav Res Ther</i> 2016;80:33-42.
Reynolds, 1986	Reynolds WM, Coats KI. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 1986;54:653-60.
Rohde, 2004	Rohde P, Clarke GN, Mace DE et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2004;43:660-8.
Rohde, 2014	Rohde P, Stice E, Shaw H et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 2014;82:65-74.
Rosselló, 1999	Rosselló J, Bernal G. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 1999;67:734-45.
Rosselló, 2012	Rosselló J, Bernal G, Rivera-Medina C. <i>Cultur Divers Ethnic Minor Psychol</i> 2008;14:234-45.
Sanford, 2006	Sanford M, Boyle M, McCleary L et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2006;45:386-495.
Santomauro, 2016	Santomauro D, Sheffield J, Sofronoff K. <i>J Autism Dev Disord</i> 2016;46:572-88.
Schniering, 2022	Schniering CA, Einstein D, Kirkman JJJ et al. <i>J Affect Disord</i> 2022;311:88-94.
Shomaker, 2017	Shomaker LB, Kelly NR, Radin RM et al. <i>Depress Anxiety</i> 2017;34:866-76.
Sorsdahl, 2024	Sorsdahl K, van der Westhuizen C, Hornsby N et al. <i>Psychother Res</i> 2024;34:96-110.
Srivastava, 2020	Srivastava P, Mehta M, Sagar R et al. <i>Asian J Psychiatr</i> 2020;50:101970.
Stallard, 2012	Stallard P, Sayal K, Phillips R et al. <i>BMJ</i> 2012;345:e6058.
Stark, 1987	Stark KD, Reynolds WM, Kaslow NJ. <i>J Abnorm Child Psychol</i> 1987;15:91-113.
Stice, 2008	Stice E, Rohde P, Seeley JR et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 2008;76:595-606.
Stikkelbroek, 2020	Stikkelbroek Y, Vink G, Nauta MH et al. <i>Sci Rep</i> 2020;10:14815
Szigethy, 2007	Szigethy E, Kenney E, Carpenter J et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2007;46:1290-8.
Tang, 2009	Tang TC, Jou SH, Ko CH et al. <i>Psychiatry Clin Neurosci</i> 2009;63:463-70.
Tompson, 2017	Tompson MC, Sugar CA, Langer DA et al. <i>J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2017;56:515-23.
Topooco, 2018	Topooco N, Berg M, Johansson S et al. <i>BJPsych Open</i> 2018;4:199-207.
Topooco, 2019	Topooco N, Byléhn S, Dahlström Nysäter E et al. <i>J Med Internet Res</i> 2019;21:e13393.
Trowell, 2007	Trowell J, Joffe I, Campbell J et al. <i>Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry</i> 2007;16:157-67.
Vostanis, 1996	Vostanis P, Feehan C, Grattan E et al. <i>Clin Child Psychol Psychiatry</i> 1996;1:199-212.
Waraan, 2021	Waraan L, Rognli EW, Czajkowski NO et al. <i>Child Adolesc Psychiatry Ment Health</i> 2021;15:8.
Weisz, 1997	Weisz JR, Thurber CA, Sweeney L et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 1997;65:703-7.
Weisz, 2009	Weisz JR, Southam-Gerow MA, Gordis EB et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 2009;77:383-96.
Wilson, 2024	Wilson J, Cestaro V, Charami-Roupa E et al. <i>Health Soc Care Deliv Res</i> 2024;12:1-121.
Wood, 1996	Wood A, Harrington R, Moore A et al. <i>J Child Psychol Psychiatry</i> 1996;37: 737-46.
Young, 2006	Young JF, Mufson L, Davies M. <i>J Child Psychol Psychiatry</i> 2006;47:1254-62.
Young, 2010	Young JF, Mufson L, Gallop R. <i>Depress Anxiety</i> 2010;27:426-33.
Young, 2016	Young JF, Benas JS, Schueler CM et al. <i>Prev Sci</i> 2016;17:314-24.
Young, 2025	Young JF, Jones JD, Schwartz KTG et al. <i>J Consult Clin Psychol</i> 2025;93:213-25.

Supplement E. Selected characteristics of included studies

<i>Study</i>	<i>Arm 1</i>	<i>Arm 2</i>	<i>Format</i>	<i>N sessions</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Age group</i>	<i>Mean age</i>	<i>Proportion women</i>	<i>Recruitment</i>	<i>Diagnosis</i>	<i>Sg</i>	<i>Ac</i>	<i>Ba</i>	<i>Itt</i>
Ackerson, 1998	cbt	wl	gsh	4	us	adol	16	0.64	com	cut-off	-	-	-	-
Andersson, 2022	bat	cau	ind	5	eu	adol	15	0.59	com	disorder	+	+	+	+
Arnarson, 2009	cbt	cau	grp	14	eu	adol	15	0.51	oth	cut-off	-	-	+	-
Asarnow, 2002	cbt	wl	ind	10	us	child		0.65	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
Bolton, 2007	ipt	wl	oth	14	oth	adol	15	0.57	oth	cut-off	+	-	+	+
Brent, 1997	cbt	fam	oth	12	us	adol	16	0.76	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Brent, 1997	cbt	sup	oth	12	us	adol	16	0.76	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Brent, 1997	fam	sup	oth	11	us	adol	16	0.76	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Casella, 2025	cbt	othctr	gsh	5	oth	child	12		com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Charkhandeh, 2016	cbt	wl	ind	24	oth	adol	15	0.54	clin	disorder	+	-	sr	-
Clarke, 1995	cbt	cau	grp	15	us	adol	15	0.70	oth	cut-off	-	-	-	-
Clarke, 1999 - no parent	cbt	wl	grp	16	us	adol	16	0.71	com	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Clarke, 1999 - parent	cbt	wl	grp	16	us	adol	16	0.71	com	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Clarke, 2001	cbt	cau	grp	15	us	adol	15	0.64	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	-
Clarke, 2002	cbt	cau	grp	16	us	adol	15	0.69	oth	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Curry, 2022	cbt	cau	ind	4	us	adol	17	0.33	com	disorder	+	-	-	-
De Cuyper, 2004	cbt	wl	grp	16	eu	child	10	0.75	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
De Jonge-Heesen, 2020	cbt	othctr	grp	8	eu	adol	14	0.64	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Diamond, 2002	fam	wl	ind	8	us	adol	15	0.78	oth	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Diamond, 2010	fam	cau	oth	12	us	adol	15	0.83	clin	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Dietz, 2015	fam	sup	fam	14	us	child	11	0.67	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Do, 2021	cbt	wl	gsh	10	eas	adol	16	0.54	oth	cut-off	+	-	sr	-
Duong, 2016	cbt	sup	grp	12	us	adol	13	0.60	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Gillham, 2006	cbt	cau	grp	12	us	child	12	0.53	com	cut-off	+	-	-	+
Goodyer, 2017	cbt	dyn	ind	20	uk	adol	15	0.75	clin	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Grudin, 2022	bat	cau	gsh	8	eu	adol	15	0.59	com	disorder	+	+	+	+
Gudmundsen, 2016	bat	cau	ind	14	us	adol	15	0.64	com	disorder	+	-	+	+
He, 2026	cbt	cau	grp	7	eas	child	12	0.60	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Idsoe, 2019	cbt	cau	grp	8	eu	adol	17	0.88	com	cut-off	-	+	sr	+
Israel, 2013	fam	cau	ind	8	eu	adol	16	0.55	clin	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Kahn, 1990	cbt	wl	grp	12	us	child	12	0.52	oth	disorder	-	-	-	+
Kahn, 1990	cbt	rel	ind	12	us	child	12	0.52	oth	disorder	-	-	-	+
Kahn, 1990	rel	wl	ind	12	us	child	12	0.52	oth	disorder	-	-	-	+
Kitchen, 2021	bat	cau	ind	6	uk	adol	16	0.82	oth	disorder	+	+	sr	-

Kobak, 2015	cbt	cau	ind	8	us	adol			clin	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Lewinsohn, 1990 - no parent	cbt	wl	grp	14	us	adol	16	0.61	com	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Lewinsohn, 1990 - parent	cbt	wl	grp	14	us	adol	16	0.65	com	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Liddle, 1990	cbt	wl	grp	8	au	child	9	0.32	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Liddle, 1990	cbt	othctr	grp	8	au	child	9	0.32	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Liddle, 1990	othctr	wl	grp	8	au	child	9	0.32	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Lindqvist, 2020	dyn	sup	gsh	6	eu	adol	17	0.80	com	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Listug-Lunde, 2013	cbt	cau	grp	13	us	child	12	0.38	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
Luby, 2012	fam	cau	ind	14	us	child	4	0.37	com	disorder	+	-	+	+
Martinez, 2019	cbt	othctr	ind	5	oth	adol	16	0.76	oth	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Martinovic, 2006	cbt	sup	grp	6	eu	adol	17	0.68	clin	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
McCarty, 2013	cbt	sup	grp	12	us	child	13	0.60	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Mechler, 2022	cbt	dyn	gsh	7	eu	adol	17	0.83	com	disorder	+	+	+	+
Mocini, 2019	cbt	cau	gsh	8	oth	adol	17	1.00	com	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Mufson, 1999	ipt	cau	ind	10	us	adol	16	0.73	clin	disorder	+	-	sr	+
Mufson, 2004	ipt	cau	ind	11	us	adol	15	0.84	clin	disorder	+	-	sr	+
O'Dea, 2024	cbt	othctr	gsh	3	au	adol	16	0.74	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Poole, 2018	fam	sup	fam	8	au	adol	15	0.73	com	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Poppelaars, 2016	cbt	cau	grp	8	eu	adol	13	1.00	oth	cut-off	-	+	sr	+
Reynolds, 1986	cbt	wl	grp	8	us	adol	16	0.63	oth	cut-off	-	-	-	-
Reynolds, 1986	cbt	rel	grp	8	us	adol	16	0.63	oth	cut-off	-	-	-	-
Reynolds, 1986	rel	wl	grp	8	us	adol	16	0.63	oth	cut-off	-	-	-	-
Rohde, 2004	cbt	othctr	grp	16	us	adol	15	0.48	oth	disorder	+	-	sr	+
Rohde, 2014	cbt	cau	grp	6	us	adol	16	0.68	com	cut-off	+	-	+	+
Rosselló, 1999	cbt	wl	oth	12	us	adol	15	0.54	oth	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Rosselló, 1999	ipt	wl	oth	12	us	adol	15	0.54	oth	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Rosselló, 1999	cbt	ipt	oth	12	us	adol	15	0.54	oth	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Rosselló, 2012	cbt	ipt	oth	12	us	adol	15	0.55	com	disorder	+	-	sr	+
Sanford, 2006	fam	cau	oth	12	can	adol	16	0.65	clin	disorder	+	+	sr	+
Santomauro, 2016	cbt	wl	grp	11	au	adol	16	0.40	com	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
Schniering, 2022	cbt	wl	gsh	8	au	adol	14	0.66	clin	disorder	+	+	+	+
Shomaker, 2017	cbt	cau	grp	6	us	adol	15	1.00	com	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
Sorsdahl, 2024	pst	othctr	ind	4	oth	adol		0.56	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Srivastava, 2020	cbt	cau	oth	12	oth	adol	16	0.24	clin	disorder	+	-	sr	+
Stallard, 2012	cbt	othctr	oth	11	uk	adol	14	0.65	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stallard, 2012	cbt	cau	oth	11	uk	adol	14	0.65	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stallard, 2012	cau	othctr	oth	11	uk	adol	14	0.65	oth	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stark, 1987	pst	wl	grp	12	us	child	11	0.43	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
Stark, 1987	bat	wl	grp	12	us	child	11	0.43	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
Stark, 1987	pst	bat	grp	12	us	child	11	0.43	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-

Stice, 2008	cbt	cau	grp	4	us	adol	16	0.56	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stice, 2008	sup	cau	grp	4	us	adol	16	0.56	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stice, 2008	cbt	sup	grp	4	us	adol	16	0.56	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Stikkelbroek, 2020	cbt	cau	ind	13	eu	adol	17	0.82	clin	disorder	+	+	+	+
Szigethy, 2007	cbt	cau	ind	10	us	adol	15	0.51	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Tang, 2009	ipt	cau	ind	12	eas	adol	15	0.66	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	+
Tompson, 2017	fam	sup	fam	12	us	adol	11	0.56	com	disorder	+	-	sr	+
Topooco, 2018	cbt	othctr	gsh	8	eu	adol	17	0.94	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Topooco, 2019	cbt	cau	oth	8	eu	adol	18	0.96	com	cut-off	+	+	sr	+
Trowell, 2007	dyn	fam	ind	25	eu	child	12	0.38	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Vostanis, 1996	cbt	othctr	ind	9	uk	child	13	0.56	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	-
Waraan, 2021	fam	cau	fam	16	eu	adol	15	1.00	clin	disorder	+	+	+	+
Weisz, 1997	cbt	cau	grp	8	us	child	10	0.46	oth	cut-off	-	-	sr	-
Weisz, 2009	cbt	cau	ind	15	us	child	12	0.56	clin	disorder	-	-	sr	+
Wilson, 2024	ipt	cau	ind	7	uk	adol	15	0.75	clin	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
Wood, 1996	cbt	rel	ind	6	uk	adol	14	0.69	clin	disorder	-	-	-	+
Young, 2006	ipt	othctr	oth	9	us	adol	13	0.85	oth	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
Young, 2010	ipt	othctr	oth	7	us	adol	15	0.59	com	cut-off	+	-	-	-
Young, 2016	ipt	othctr	oth	11	us	adol	14	0.67	com	cut-off	+	-	sr	+
Young, 2025	ipt	cau	oth	6	us	adol	15	0.65	oth	cut-off	+	-	sr	+

Ac: allocation concealment; Adol: adolescents; au: Australia; Ba: blinded assessment; bat: behavioral activation therapy; can: Canada; cau: care-as-usual; cbt: cognitive behavior therapy; clin: clinical; com: community; cut-off: score above cut-off on validated measure; disorder: diagnosis of depressive disorder; dyn: psychodynamic therapy; eas: East Asia; eu: Europe; fam: family therapy; grp: group; gsh: guided self-help; ind: individual; ipt: interpersonal therapy; Itt: intention-to-treat analysis; oth: other; othctr: other control condition; pst: problem-solving therapy; rel: relaxation therapy; Sg: sequence generation; sr: self-report; sup: supportive therapy; uk: United Kingdom; us: United States of America; wl: waiting list.

Supplement F. Studies excluded because of type of therapy

<i>Reference</i>	<i>Therapy</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Kahn, 1990	Self-modeling	Kahn JS, Kehle TJ, Jenson WR et al. Sch Psychol Rev 1990;19:196-211.
Makover, 2019	High School Transition Program (HSTP)	Makover H, Adrian M, Wilks C et al. Prev Sci 2019;20:499-509.
Bluth, 2024	Mindful self-compassion for teens (MSC-T)	Bluth K, Lathren C, Park J et al. J Adolesc 2024;96:322-36.
Fine, 1991	Social skills training	Fine S, Forth A, Gilbert M et al. J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry 1991;30:79-85.
Reed, 1994	Social skills training	Reed MK. Adolescence 1994;29:293-302.
Shirk, 2014	Mindfulness-based	Shirk SR, DePrince AP, Crisostomo PS et al. Psychotherapy 2014;51:167-79.
Hayes, 2011	Acceptance and commitment therapy	Hayes L, Boyd CP, Sewell J. Mindfulness 2011;2:86-94.

Supplement G. Trials contributing more than one comparison to the network meta-analysis

	<i>Comparisons included in network meta-analysis</i>
<i>Studies with 3 conditions</i>	
Brent, 1997	CBT vs FAM
	CBT vs SUP
	FAM vs SUP
Kahn, 1990	CBT vs WL
	CBT vs REL
	REL vs WL
Liddle, 1990	CBT vs WL
	CBT vs OthCTR
	WL vs OthCTR
Reynolds, 1986	CBT vs WL
	CBT vs REL
	REL vs WL
Rossellò, 1999	CBT vs WL
	IPT vs WL
	CBT vs IPT
Stallard, 2012	CBT vs OthCTR
	CBT vs CAU
	CAU vs OthCTR
Stark, 1987	PST vs WL
	BAT vs WL
	PST vs BAT
Stice, 2008	CBT vs CAU
	SUP vs CAU
	CBT vs SUP
<i>Studies contributing two comparisons</i>	
Clarke, 1999	CBT with parent component
	CBT without parent component
Lewinsohn, 1990	CBT with parent component
	CBT without parent component

Conditions

CBT: cognitive behavior therapy
 IPT: interpersonal therapy
 BAT: behavioral activation therapy
 FAM: family therapy
 SUP: supportive therapy
 REL: relaxation therapy
 DYN: psychodynamic therapy
 PST: problem-solving therapy
 CAU: care-as-usual
 WL: waiting list
 OthCTR: other control conditions

Supplement H. Pairwise meta-analyses

Comparison	Model	n	g	95% CI	I ²	95% CI	PI
cbt-cau	Main	22	0.23	[0.06; 0.39]	68.72	[51.46; 79.84]	[-0.36; 0.81]
cbt-cau	Outliers excl.	20	0.29	[0.14; 0.43]	47.34	[11.33; 68.73]	[-0.15; 0.72]
cbt-cau	Only RoB > 2	11	0.30	[0.03; 0.58]	81.38	[67.77; 89.24]	[-0.49; 1.1]
cbt-wl	Main	15	0.81	[0.50; 1.11]	71.15	[51.32; 82.91]	[-0.22; 1.83]
cbt-wl	Outliers excl.	14	0.66	[0.44; 0.88]	17.98	[0; 55.72]	[0.29; 1.03]
cbt-wl	Only RoB > 2	2	0.56	[0.16; 0.95]	0	-	[-1.91; 3.02]
cbt-othctr	Main	9	0.56	[-0.05; 1.18]	95.44	[93.15; 96.96]	[-1.33; 2.46]
cbt-othctr	Outliers excl.	8	0.25	[0.07; 0.43]	43.56	[0; 75.03]	[-0.11; 0.62]
cbt-othctr	Only RoB > 2	7	0.62	[-0.19; 1.43]	96.54	[94.67; 97.75]	[-1.64; 2.88]
cbt-sup	Main	5	0.40	[0.26; 0.55]	0	[0; 79.2]	[0.15; 0.66]
cbt-sup	Outliers excl.	5	0.40	[0.26; 0.55]	0	[0; 79.2]	[0.15; 0.66]
cbt-sup	Only RoB > 2	3	0.42	[0.03; 0.81]	0	[0; 89.6]	[-0.07; 0.91]
fam-cau	Main	5	0.15	[-0.33; 0.62]	32.4	[0; 74.27]	[-0.62; 0.91]
fam-cau	Outliers excl.	5	0.15	[-0.33; 0.62]	32.4	[0; 74.27]	[-0.62; 0.91]
fam-cau	Only RoB > 2	5	0.15	[-0.33; 0.62]	32.4	[0; 74.27]	[-0.62; 0.91]
ipt-cau	Main	5	0.45	[0.05; 0.84]	54.17	[0; 83.11]	[-0.42; 1.31]
ipt-cau	Outliers excl.	5	0.45	[0.05; 0.84]	54.17	[0; 83.11]	[-0.42; 1.31]
ipt-cau	Only RoB > 2	4	0.29	[-0.09; 0.67]	7.28	[0; 85.8]	[-0.39; 0.97]
fam-sup	Main	4	0.31	[-0.41; 1.03]	58.69	[0; 86.25]	[-0.89; 1.51]
fam-sup	Outliers excl.	4	0.31	[-0.41; 1.03]	58.69	[0; 86.25]	[-0.89; 1.51]
fam-sup	Only RoB > 2	2	0.18	[-1.46; 1.83]	0	[-; -]	[-1.7; 2.07]
bat-cau	Main	4	0.64	[0.11; 1.17]	0	[0; 84.69]	[-0.13; 1.41]
bat-cau	Outliers excl.	4	0.64	[0.11; 1.17]	0	[0; 84.69]	[-0.13; 1.41]
bat-cau	Only RoB > 2	4	0.64	[0.11; 1.17]	0	[0; 84.69]	[-0.13; 1.41]
cbt-rel	Main	3	0.32	[-0.27; 0.91]	0	[0; 89.6]	[-0.56; 1.2]
cbt-rel	Outliers excl.	3	0.32	[-0.27; 0.91]	0	[0; 89.6]	[-0.56; 1.2]
cbt-rel	Only RoB > 2	3	0.32	[-0.27; 0.91]	0	[0; 89.6]	[-0.56; 1.2]

Conditions

RoB: risk of bias; PI: prediction intervals

cbt: cognitive behavior therapy
 ipt: interpersonal therapy
 bat: behavioral activation therapy
 fam: family therapy
 sup: supportive therapy
 rel: relaxation therapy
 dyn: psychodynamic therapy
 pst: problem-solving therapy
 cau: care-as-usual
 wl: waiting list
 othctr: other control conditions

Supplement I. Transitivity assessment: characteristics of included studies across different comparisons

Comparison	n	Depressive disorder	Clinical recruitment	Adolescents	Country			Format			Number of sessions			Low RoB
					North America	Europe	Other country	Individual	Group	Other / mixed	<8	9-12	>12	
bat-cau	4	4 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	2 (50.0)
cbt-cau	22	6 (27.3)	4 (18.2)	17 (77.3)	13 (59.1)	6 (27.3)	3 (13.6)	5 (22.7)	13 (59.1)	4 (18.2)	11 (50.0)	4 (18.2)	7 (31.8)	6 (27.3)
cbt-othctr	9	3 (33.3)	1 (11.1)	6 (66.7)	1 (11.1)	4 (44.4)	4 (44.4)	2 (22.2)	3 (33.3)	4 (44.4)	6 (66.7)	2 (22.2)	1 (11.1)	6 (66.7)
cbt-rel	3	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
cbt-sup	5	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	4 (80.0)	4 (80.0)	1 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (80.0)	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (40.0)
cbt-wl	15	8 (53.3)	2 (13.3)	11 (73.3)	9 (60.0)	1 (6.7)	5 (33.3)	2 (13.3)	9 (60.0)	4 (26.7)	4 (26.7)	5 (33.3)	6 (40.0)	1 (6.7)
fam-cau	5	4 (80.0)	4 (80.0)	4 (80.0)	3 (60.0)	2 (40.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (40.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (60.0)	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	2 (40.0)	4 (80.0)
fam-sup	4	4 (100.0)	2 (50.0)	3 (75.0)	3 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)	1 (25.0)	2 (50.0)	1 (25.0)	1 (25.0)
ipt-cau	5	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	5 (100.0)	3 (60.0)	1 (20.0)	1 (20.0)	4 (80.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20.0)	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)

We only report the characteristics for comparisons with at least 3 studies

Conditions

RoB: risk of bias

cbt: cognitive behavior therapy
 ipt: interpersonal therapy
 bat: behavioral activation therapy
 fam: family therapy
 sup: supportive therapy
 rel: relaxation therapy
 cau: care-as-usual
 wl: waiting list
 othctr: other control conditions

Supplement J. Proportion of direct evidence for each comparison in the main network meta-analysis

Supplement K. Difference between direct and indirect evidence

<i>Comparison</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>NMA</i>	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Indirect</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>
bat:cau	4	0.64	0.70	0.38	0.32	0.48	0.63
bat:pst	1	0.54	0.15	0.93	-0.79	-0.93	0.35
bat:wl	1	1.16	1.17	1.21	-0.04	-0.06	0.95
cbt:cau	22	0.28	0.24	0.43	-0.19	-0.72	0.47
fam:cau	5	0.20	0.17	0.24	-0.07	-0.21	0.84
ipt:cau	5	0.35	0.47	0.23	0.24	0.74	0.46
othctr:cau	1	-0.31	-0.29	-0.33	0.05	0.11	0.92
sup:cau	1	-0.18	0.21	-0.25	0.46	0.95	0.34
cbt:dyn	2	0.10	0.09	0.11	-0.02	-0.04	0.97
cbt:fam	1	0.08	0.37	0.04	0.33	0.63	0.53
cbt:ipt	2	-0.06	0.05	-0.11	0.16	0.42	0.68
cbt:othctr	9	0.59	0.56	0.53	0.03	0.10	0.92
cbt:sup	5	0.46	0.45	0.62	-0.17	-0.45	0.65
cbt:wl	15	0.80	0.81	0.69	0.13	0.36	0.72
dyn:fam	1	-0.02	-0.51	0.19	-0.70	-1.23	0.22
dyn:sup	1	0.36	0.84	0.17	0.68	1.19	0.23
fam:sup	4	0.38	0.32	0.47	-0.15	-0.39	0.70
fam:wl	1	0.71	0.65	0.73	-0.07	-0.12	0.90
ipt:othctr	3	0.65	0.72	0.61	0.10	0.29	0.77
ipt:wl	2	0.86	0.63	0.95	-0.32	-0.79	0.43
othctr:pst	1	-0.41	-0.11	-0.87	0.76	1.03	0.30
othctr:wl	1	0.21	-0.33	0.26	-0.60	-0.95	0.34
pst:wl	1	0.62	1.02	0.28	0.74	0.92	0.36
rel:wl	2	0.75	1.19	0.33	0.86	1.28	0.20

Overall difference between direct and indirect effects: $Q=10.58$; $df=21$; $p=0.970$

Supplement L. Net heat plot

Supplement M. Comparison-adjusted funnel plot

Supplement N. GRADE assessment

The analysis of the certainty of the evidence was performed with the online application CINeMA, which follows the principles of the GRADE methodology. The following criteria were applied:

- Within-study bias: the “overall” risk of bias of each study was calculated as follows: (a) Low risk if all four domains were judged as “low risk”; (b) Some concerns if there were 2 or 3 domains were judged as “low risk”; and (c) high risk when none or one domains were judged as “low risk”. For each comparison, the histogram was interpreted according to a “Majority RoB” rule (Papakonstantinou et al., 2020);
- Reporting bias was set at low risk of bias for all comparisons, because this was not rated
- Across-studies bias was considered “undetected” when was not possible to evaluate the risk of publication bias;
- Imprecision: an effect size between 0.24 was considered as clinically important size of effect;
- Heterogeneity: an effect size of 0.24 was considered as clinically important size of effect;
- Incoherence: for all the comparisons for which only a direct or indirect estimation was available (Inconsistency measures: Not applicable) we reported “some concerns”.

The Confidence rating was defined as follows:

- Very low: Two or more domains were rated with “major concerns” (with or without more domains rated as “some concerns”); OR: One domain was rated as “major concerns” and three or more as “some concerns”
- Low: One domain was rated as “major concerns” and two with “some concerns”
- Moderate: One domain was rated as “major concerns” and no more than one with “some concerns”; or three or more domains were rated as “some concerns”.
- High: Not more than 2 domains with “some concerns”

Comparison	Number of Studies	Within-study bias	Reporting bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Heterogeneity	Incoherence	Confidence rating	R
Mixed evidence									
bat vs cau	4	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
bat vs pst	1	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Very low	
bat vs wl	1	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	No concerns	No concerns	High	
cau vs cbt	22	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cau vs fam	5	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	High	
cau vs ipt	5	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cau vs othctr	1	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cau vs sup	1	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	High	
cbt vs dyn	2	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cbt vs fam	1	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cbt vs ipt	2	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cbt vs othctr	9	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cbt vs rel	3	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Very low	
cbt vs sup	5	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
cbt vs wl	15	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
dyn vs fam	1	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
dyn vs sup	1	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	High	
fam vs sup	4	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
fam vs wl	1	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
ipt vs othctr	3	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	High	
ipt vs wl	2	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	High	
othctr vs pst	1	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
othctr vs wl	1	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	Moderate	
pst vs wl	1	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	No concerns	Low	
rel vs wl	2	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Very low	

Indirect evidence

bat vs cbt	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Very low
bat vs dyn	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Low
bat vs fam	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Low
bat vs ipt	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
bat vs othctr	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Moderate
bat vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
bat vs sup	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Moderate
cau vs dyn	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
cau vs pst	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
cau vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
cau vs wl	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Major concerns	Very low
cbt vs pst	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
dyn vs ipt	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
dyn vs othctr	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Low
dyn vs pst	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
dyn vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
dyn vs wl	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Major concerns	Very low
fam vs ipt	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
fam vs othctr	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Major concerns	Very low
fam vs pst	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
fam vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
ipt vs pst	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
ipt vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
ipt vs sup	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Major concerns	Very low
othctr vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Very low
othctr vs sup	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	High
pst vs rel	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
pst vs sup	--	No concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
rel vs sup	--	Major concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Major concerns	No concerns	Major concerns	Very low
sup vs wl	--	Some concerns	Low risk	No concerns	Some concerns	Some concerns	Major concerns	Very low

Supplement O. Sensitivity analyses: Only adolescents

O.1. Netleague table

Behavioral activation										
0.68 (0.20, 1.15)	Care-as-usual									
0.40 (-0.09, 0.90)	-0.27 (-0.43, -0.12)	Cognitive behavior therapy								
0.36 (-0.26, 0.99)	-0.31 (-0.72, 0.09)	-0.04 (-0.42, 0.34)	Psychodynamic therapy							
0.60 (0.03, 1.16)	-0.08 (-0.38, 0.22)	0.19 (-0.11, 0.50)	0.23 (-0.23, 0.70)	Family therapy						
0.32 (-0.21, 0.86)	-0.35 (-0.60, -0.11)	-0.08 (-0.32, 0.16)	-0.04 (-0.49, 0.41)	-0.27 (-0.64, 0.10)	Interpersonal therapy					
0.80 (0.26, 1.34)	0.12 (-0.13, 0.37)	0.39 (0.17, 0.62)	0.43 (-0.01, 0.87)	0.20 (-0.17, 0.57)	0.47 (0.19, 0.75)	Other control				
0.69 (-0.19, 1.57)	0.01 (-0.72, 0.75)	0.29 (-0.44, 1.02)	0.33 (-0.49, 1.15)	0.10 (-0.69, 0.88)	0.37 (-0.38, 1.12)	-0.11 (-0.80, 0.59)	Problem-solving therapy			
0.48 (-0.31, 1.28)	-0.20 (-0.83, 0.44)	0.08 (-0.54, 0.70)	0.12 (-0.61, 0.84)	-0.11 (-0.80, 0.58)	0.16 (-0.51, 0.82)	-0.32 (-0.98, 0.34)	-0.21 (-1.17, 0.75)	Relaxation therapy		
0.82 (0.26, 1.38)	0.14 (-0.16, 0.44)	0.41 (0.13, 0.70)	0.46 (0.03, 0.88)	0.22 (-0.10, 0.54)	0.49 (0.13, 0.86)	0.02 (-0.34, 0.38)	0.13 (-0.65, 0.91)	0.34 (-0.34, 1.02)	Supportive therapy	
1.25 (0.70, 1.79)	0.57 (0.30, 0.83)	0.84 (0.61, 1.07)	0.88 (0.44, 1.32)	0.65 (0.29, 1.01)	0.92 (0.62, 1.22)	0.45 (0.14, 0.76)	0.55 (-0.21, 1.31)	0.76 (0.12, 1.41)	0.43 (0.07, 0.78)	Waiting list

O.2. Ranking of treatments: P-score

Treatment	<i>Effects</i>
BAT	0.93
IPT	0.76
CBT	0.70
REL	0.62
FAM	0.61
DYN	0.59
PST	0.51
CAU	0.38
SUP	0.23
Other control	0.14
Waiting list	0.02

O.3. Direct versus indirect effects

<i>Comparison</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>NMA</i>	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Indirect</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>p-value</i>
bat vs cau	4	0.64	0.7	0.38	0.32	0.63
bat vs pst	1	0.54	0.13	0.88	-0.75	0.37
bat vs wl	1	1.16	1.19	1.15	0.04	0.95
cbt vs cau	22	0.28	0.24	0.47	-0.23	0.32
fam vs cau	5	0.20	0.17	0.24	-0.07	0.84
ipt vs cau	5	0.35	0.47	0.23	0.24	0.45
othctr vs cau	1	-0.31	-0.29	-0.31	0.02	0.97
sup vs cau	1	-0.18	0.20	-0.26	0.46	0.34
cbt vs dyn	2	0.10	0.09	0.11	-0.02	0.97
cbt vs fam	1	0.08	0.38	0.04	0.34	0.51
cbt vs ipt	2	-0.06	0.05	-0.10	0.15	0.69
cbt vs othctr	9	0.59	0.56	0.69	-0.13	0.67
cbt vs rel	3	0.05	0.28	-1.12	1.40	0.08
cbt vs sup	5	0.46	0.44	0.50	-0.06	0.86
cbt vs wl	15	0.8	0.81	0.76	0.05	0.88
dyn vs fam	1	-0.02	-0.51	0.19	-0.70	0.22
dyn vs sup	1	0.36	0.84	0.17	0.68	0.23
fam vs sup	4	0.38	0.32	0.46	-0.14	0.72
fam vs wl	1	0.71	0.65	0.72	-0.07	0.90
ipt vs othctr	3	0.65	0.72	0.61	0.11	0.77
ipt vs wl	2	0.86	0.64	0.96	-0.32	0.43
othctr vs pst	1	-0.41	-0.11	-0.87	0.76	0.30
othctr vs wl	1	0.21	-0.34	0.26	-0.60	0.34
pst vs wl	1	0.62	1.00	0.41	0.59	0.46
rel vs wl	2	0.74	1.23	0.21	1.03	0.09

Overall difference between direct and indirect effects: $Q=15.57$; $df=16$; $p=0.48$

O.4. Net heat plot

Supplement P. Sensitivity analyses: Only low risk of bias

P.1. Netleague table

Behavioral activation								
0.96 (-0.04, 1.97)	Care-as-usual							
0.60 (-0.51, 1.71)	-0.36 (-0.82, 0.10)	Cognitive behavior therapy						
0.53 (-0.78, 1.83)	-0.44 (-1.26, 0.39)	-0.08 (-0.79, 0.64)	Psychodynamic therapy					
0.78 (-0.39, 1.96)	-0.18 (-0.78, 0.42)	0.18 (-0.54, 0.90)	0.26 (-0.71, 1.23)	Family therapy				
1.32 (0.14, 2.51)	0.36 (-0.27, 0.98)	0.72 (0.25, 1.19)	0.80 (-0.06, 1.65)	0.54 (-0.30, 1.37)	Other control			
1.22 (-0.48, 2.92)	0.25 (-1.12, 1.62)	0.61 (-0.69, 1.92)	0.69 (-0.80, 2.18)	0.43 (-1.05, 1.91)	-0.11 (-1.32, 1.11)	Problem-solving therapy		
0.99 (-0.23, 2.21)	0.03 (-0.66, 0.71)	0.39 (-0.26, 1.03)	0.46 (-0.36, 1.28)	0.20 (-0.59, 0.99)	-0.33 (-1.12, 0.45)	-0.23 (-1.68, 1.22)	Supportive therapy	
1.14 (-0.50, 2.79)	0.18 (-1.12, 1.48)	0.54 (-0.67, 1.76)	0.62 (-0.79, 2.03)	0.36 (-1.05, 1.77)	-0.18 (-1.48, 1.13)	-0.07 (-1.86, 1.71)	0.16 (-1.22, 1.53)	Waiting list

P.2. Ranking of treatments: P-score

Treatment	<i>Effects</i>
BAT	0.91
DYN	0.73
CBT	0.71
FAM	0.55
CAU	0.40
SUP	0.39
WL	0.34
PST	0.31
Other control	0.16

P.3. Direct versus indirect effects

<i>Comparison</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>NMA</i>	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Indirect</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>p-value</i>
cbt vs cau	6	0.36	0.28	0.98	-0.70	0.33
fam vs cau	4	0.18	0.23	-0.09	0.32	0.70
othctr vs cau	1	-0.36	-0.29	-0.39	0.10	0.89
sup vs cau	1	-0.03	0.20	-0.14	0.34	0.65
cbt vs dyn	2	-0.08	0.09	-0.58	0.68	0.42
cbt vs othctr	6	0.72	0.69	1.40	-0.71	0.54
cbt vs sup	2	0.39	0.38	0.40	-0.02	0.97
dyn vs sup	1	0.46	0.84	0.17	0.68	0.42
fam vs sup	1	0.20	0.01	0.33	-0.32	0.70

Overall difference between direct and indirect effects: $Q=1.83$; $df=6$; $p=0.93$

P.4. Net heat plot

Supplement Q. Sensitivity analyses: Only waiting list control conditions

Q.1. Netleague table

Behavioral activation								
0.34 (-0.87; 1.54)	Cognitive behavior therapy							
0.44 (-0.82; 1.70)	0.10 (-0.28; 0.49)	Psychodynamic therapy						
0.42 (-0.84; 1.68)	0.08 (-0.30; 0.47)	-0.02 (-0.47; 0.43)	Family therapy					
0.51 (-0.74; 1.77)	0.18 (-0.25; 0.61)	0.07 (-0.50; 0.64)	0.09 (-0.48; 0.66)	Interpersonal therapy				
0.14 (-0.95; 1.24)	-0.19 (-1.36; 0.97)	-0.30 (-1.52; 0.92)	-0.28 (-1.49; 0.94)	-0.37 (-1.59; 0.85)	Problem-solving therapy			
0.42 (-0.87; 1.71)	0.08 (-0.42; 0.59)	-0.02 (-0.65; 0.61)	0.00 (-0.63; 0.63)	-0.09 (-0.74; 0.56)	0.28 (-0.98; 1.53)	Relaxation therapy		
0.82 (-0.42; 2.06)	0.48 (0.18; 0.78)	0.38 (-0.04; 0.79)	0.40 (0.05; 0.74)	0.30 (-0.22; 0.83)	0.67 (-0.52; 1.87)	0.40 (-0.19; 0.98)	Supportive therapy	
1.17 (-0.01; 2.35)	0.83 (0.61; 1.05)	0.72 (0.29; 1.16)	0.75 (0.32; 1.17)	0.65 (0.22; 1.08)	1.02 (-0.12; 2.16)	0.75 (0.22; 1.27)	0.35 (-0.02; 0.71)	Waiting list

Q.2. Ranking of treatments: P-score

Treatment	<i>Effects</i>
BAT	0.78
PST	0.70
CBT	0.68
FAM	0.57
REL	0.56
DYN	0.54
IPT	0.47
SUP	0.18
WL	0.01

Q.3. Direct versus indirect effects

<i>Comparison</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>NMA</i>	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Indirect</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>p-value</i>
cbt vs dyn	2	0.11	0.09	0.13	-0.03	0.94
cbt vs fam	1	0.08	0.38	-0.01	0.39	0.40
cbt vs ipt	2	0.18	0.08	0.33	-0.25	0.57
cbt vs rel	3	0.08	0.29	-1.04	1.33	0.06
cbt vs sup	5	0.48	0.43	0.65	-0.22	0.56
cbt vs wl	15	0.83	0.81	0.97	-0.16	0.67
dyn vs fam	1	-0.02	-0.51	0.23	-0.74	0.13
dyn vs sup	1	0.38	0.84	0.19	0.65	0.17
fam vs sup	4	0.4	0.31	0.67	-0.36	0.38
fam vs wl	1	0.75	0.65	0.77	-0.12	0.83
ipt vs wl	2	0.65	0.63	0.69	-0.06	0.89
rel vs wl	2	0.75	1.22	0.25	0.97	0.07

Overall difference between direct and indirect effects: $Q=7,76$; $df=10$; $p=0.65$

Q.4. Net heat plot

Supplement R. Network meta-analysis of study drop-out: Relative risks

R.1. Netleague table

Behavioral activation										
0.82 (0.43; 1.53)	Care-as-usual									
0.93 (0.49; 1.79)	1.14 (0.98; 1.33)	Cognitive behavior therapy								
0.94 (0.43; 2.03)	1.15 (0.74; 1.79)	1.00 (0.66; 1.53)	Psychodynamic therapy							
0.92 (0.42; 1.99)	1.13 (0.72; 1.76)	0.98 (0.63; 1.55)	0.98 (0.53; 1.80)	Family therapy						
0.88 (0.41; 1.92)	1.08 (0.69; 1.71)	0.95 (0.60; 1.49)	0.94 (0.51; 1.74)	0.96 (0.51; 1.80)	Interpersonal therapy					
0.93 (0.47; 1.88)	1.15 (0.85; 1.54)	1.00 (0.78; 1.29)	1.00 (0.61; 1.63)	1.02 (0.61; 1.71)	1.06 (0.64; 1.75)	Other control				
0.98 (0.42; 2.31)	1.21 (0.68; 2.15)	1.05 (0.60; 1.84)	1.05 (0.52; 2.10)	1.07 (0.52; 2.19)	1.11 (0.55; 2.26)	1.05 (0.64; 1.73)	Problem-solving therapy			
1.02 (0.34; 3.10)	1.25 (0.50; 3.12)	1.09 (0.44; 2.70)	1.09 (0.40; 2.94)	1.11 (0.41; 3.05)	1.16 (0.43; 3.13)	1.09 (0.43; 2.79)	1.04 (0.36; 2.99)	Relaxation therapy		
0.87 (0.39; 1.91)	1.06 (0.66; 1.71)	0.93 (0.58; 1.49)	0.92 (0.50; 1.72)	0.94 (0.62; 1.43)	0.98 (0.51; 1.87)	0.93 (0.54; 1.59)	0.88 (0.42; 1.83)	0.85 (0.31; 2.35)	Supportive therapy	
0.88 (0.42; 1.81)	1.08 (0.75; 1.54)	0.94 (0.68; 1.31)	0.94 (0.55; 1.59)	0.95 (0.55; 1.67)	0.99 (0.60; 1.63)	0.94 (0.62; 1.42)	0.89 (0.47; 1.70)	0.86 (0.34; 2.15)	1.01 (0.57; 1.80)	Waiting list

R.2. Ranking of treatments: P-score

Treatment	<i>P-score</i>
BAT	0.59
REL	0.59
PST	0.59
CBT	0.56
Other control	0.54
DYN	0.54
FAM	0.51
IPT	0.45
WL	0.43
SUP	0.42
CAU	0.27

R.3. Direct versus indirect effects

<i>Comparison</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Proportion</i>	<i>NMA</i>	<i>Direct</i>	<i>Indirect</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>p-value</i>
cau vs cbt	16	0.94	1.14	1.16	0.94	1.23	0.54
cau vs fam	4	0.63	1.13	1.03	1.30	0.79	0.62
cau vs ipt	4	0.49	1.08	1.00	1.18	0.85	0.72
cau vs sup	1	0.05	1.06	1.05	1.06	0.98	0.99
cbt vs dyn	2	0.97	1.00	1.01	0.82	1.23	0.86
cbt vs fam	1	0.10	0.98	0.95	0.99	0.96	0.95
cbt vs ipt	2	0.22	0.95	0.99	0.94	1.06	0.92
cbt vs othctr	6	0.97	1.00	1.01	0.73	1.39	0.66
cbt vs rel	2	0.85	1.09	1.15	0.84	1.37	0.81
cbt vs sup	5	0.56	0.93	1.03	0.81	1.27	0.63
cbt vs wl	11	0.90	0.94	0.94	0.94	1.00	1.00
dyn vs sup	1	0.08	0.92	1.12	0.91	1.23	0.86
fam vs sup	4	0.78	0.94	0.89	1.17	0.76	0.59
ipt vs othctr	2	0.14	1.06	0.80	1.11	0.72	0.66
ipt vs wl	2	0.44	0.99	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.99
rel vs wl	1	0.57	0.86	0.91	0.79	1.15	0.88

Overall difference between direct and indirect effects: $Q=0.74$; $df=13$; $p=1.00$

R.4. Net heat plot

